

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 113

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 113

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 113:1 ¹Praise ²the LORD! ^aPraise, O ^bservants of the LORD, Praise the name of the LORD.</p> <p>² ^aBlessed be the name of the LORD From this time forth and forever.</p> <p>³ ^aFrom the rising of the sun to its setting The ^bname of the LORD is to be praised.</p> <p>⁴ The LORD is ^ahigh above all nations; His ^bglory is above the heavens.</p> <p>Psa. 113:5 ^aWho is like the LORD our God, Who ^bis enthroned on high, Who ^{1a}humbles Himself to behold <i>The things that are</i> in heaven and in the earth? He ^araises the poor from the dust And lifts the needy from the ash heap, To make <i>them</i> ^asit with ¹princes, With the ¹princes of His people. He ^amakes the barren woman abide in the house As a joyful mother of children. ¹Praise ²the LORD!</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">הִלְלוּ יְהוָה הִלְלוּ עַבְדֵי יְהוָה הִלְלוּ אֶת־שֵׁם יְהוָה : ² יְהִי שֵׁם יְהוָה מְבֹרָךְ מֵעַתָּה וְעַד־עוֹלָם : ³ מִמִּזְרַח־שֶׁמֶשׁ עַד־מְבֹאֵז מִהַלְלֵי שֵׁם יְהוָה : ⁴ רָם עַל־כָּל־גּוֹיִם יְהוָה עַל הַשָּׁמַיִם כְּבוֹדוֹ : ⁵ מִי כִּי־יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ הַמְּגִבִּיהִי לַשָּׁבֶת : ⁶ הַמְּשַׁפִּילִי לָרְאוֹת בַּשָּׁמַיִם וּבָאָרֶץ : מִמִּקְיָמִי מֵעַפְרָה דָל מֵאֲשַׁפֵּת יָרִים אֲבִיוֹן : ⁷ לְהוֹשִׁיבִי עִם־נְדִיבִים עִם נְדִיבֵי עַמּוֹ : ⁸ מוֹשִׁיבִי אֶעֱקֶרֶת הַבַּיִת אִם־הַבְּנִים שְׂמֵחָה הִלְלוּ־ יְהוָה :</p>

References

Psalm 113:1

¹Or *Hallelujah! Praise*

²Heb *YAH*

^aPs 135:1

^bPs 34:22; 69:36; 79:10; 90:13

Psalm 113:2

^aPs 145:21; Dan 2:20

Psalm 113:3

^aPs 50:1; Is 59:19; Mal 1:11

^bPs 18:3; 48:1, 10

Psalm 113:4

^aPs 97:9; 99:2

^bPs 8:1; 57:11; 148:13

Psalm 113:5

^aEx 15:11; Ps 35:10; 89:6

^bPs 103:19

Psalm 113:6

¹Or *looks far below in the heavens and on the earth?*

^aPs 11:4; 138:6; Is 57:15

Psalm 113:7

^a1 Sam 2:8; Ps 107:41

Psalm 113:8

¹Or *nobles*

^aJob 36:7

Psalm 113:9

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^a1 Sam 2:5; Ps 68:6; Is 54:1

Targum

Psa. 113:1 Hallelujah! Give praise, O servants of the LORD, praise the name of the LORD. ² May the name of the LORD be blessed, from now and forever. ³ From the rising of the sun to its setting, the name of the LORD is praised. ⁴ The LORD is high above all Gentiles, his glory is over the heavens. ⁵ Who is like the LORD, our God, whose dwelling is lofty in situation? ⁶ Who lowers his eyes to look on the heavens and the earth. ⁷ Who raises up the poor man from the dust; he will lift up the needy from the ash-heap. ⁸ To make him dwell with the leaders, with the leaders of his people. ⁹ Who makes dwell the congregation of Israel, who is likened to a barren woman who sits beholding the men of her house, full of people, like a mother who rejoices over her sons.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

Psalms 113-118 are a series called the “Hallel.” These are uplifting Psalms for the Jewish nation. They have sung these Psalms for millennia as the people wandered around the world. These Psalms have kept the people alive during days of trial.

Notes on the Psalm

The name of the LORD is to be praised. Even though today the actual pronunciation of the name is unknown, it is still praised. The name of the LORD was uttered by the High Priest in the Holy of Holies in the Temple at Jerusalem. It was said once a year on Yom Kippur at 3:00 PM when the sacrifice for the forgiveness of the people was made. When the Temple was destroyed the High Priest determined that there was no way to share the name. Therefore, the pronunciation was not passed onto the next High Priest. When the name of the LORD is encountered, the people say the word Adonai. The utterance of the name was forbidden. There is a story in the Torah about two of Aaron’s sons dying because they uttered the name of the LORD when they were outside the Holy of Holies in the Tabernacle in the desert.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

